

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
1.0	2024-04-30	Mateo Rejón López	Document setup

1 Assembled Validation Test Stand

This document gives an overview of the hardware placement of the assembled validation test stand. The individual subsystems are described in separate deliverables (D3.2-D3.8).

The Validation Test Stand utilizes an existing thermal-vacuum chamber setup in the CoPhy Laboratory of TUBS. The subsystems are partially placed inside the TVAC and partially around the TVAC, and are connected between each other with fluidic and electrical interfaces. Figure 1-1 and Figure 1-2 show the placement of the various LUWEX subsystems.

Figure 1-1: Photo of the TVAC setup with the positions of all the subsystems. (Note: TVAC front wall not attached yet.)

Figure 1-2: Placement of LIBS PC and laser water chiller (left) and placement of the LIBS laser compartment (right), behind the TVAC.

The experiment control is executed from a neighbouring room, the so-called control room. Figure 1-3 shows this control room with its various working places. There are separate places e.g. to control the vacuum chamber infrastructure (right side), the water extraction and capturing subsystem (middle row left place), the water purification and quality monitoring subsystem (front row left place), the mass spectrometer and cameras (front row right place) and the LIBS subsystem (middle row right place).

Figure 1-3: View into the control room of the CoPhy laboratory.